

Supplementary Information for:

Palpimanoid spiders: Burma Terrane shows Gondwanan affinities and served as a ferry transporting Gondwanan lineages to the Northern Hemisphere

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Appendix 1: List of Morphological Characters

Carapace

1. Posterior lateral eye spine: (0) absent; (1) present.
2. Anterior lateral eye spine: (0) absent; (1) present.
3. Posterior head spine pair, dorsal: (0) absent; (1) present.
4. Anterior head spine pair: (0) absent; (1) present.
5. Lateral head spine pair: (0) absent; (1) present.
6. Posterior head spine pair, positioned more ventral, mid-carapace: (0) absent; (1) present.
7. Carapace spine length: (0) long; (1) short.
8. Head spines on protuberance: (0) absent; (1) present.
9. LEs on pronounced tubercle, as large as LE diameter: (0) absent; (1) present.
10. AME: (0) present; (1) absent.
11. AME bulging forward, buggy: (0) absent; (1) present.
12. PME larger than all other eyes: (0) absent; (1) present. We follow Guo et al (2021) in their diagramming of Lagonomegopidae eyes.
13. PME positioned on anterolateral of carapace: (0) absent; (1) present.
14. AME larger than all other eyes (or larger than LEs in the case that the PMEs are larger than the LEs): (0) absent - AME equal to or smaller than other eyes; (1) present - AME larger than other eyes. *Stenochilus* has large PME, but AME are still larger than LEs.
15. AME on a large bulge that orients eye lateral: (0) absent; (1) present.
16. AME nearly contiguous with PME (less than one PME diameter away from PME): (0) absent; (1) present.

17. Distinct setae between or immediately anterior to AMEs that is curved towards posterior: (0) absent; (1) present.
18. Distance between median eyes, measured from inner lateral margin of eyes (not the center of the eyes): (0) distance between AMEs less than distance between PMEs; (1) distance between PMEs less than distance between AMEs; (2) distance between AMEs and PMEs equal.
19. LEs contiguous (separated by less than diameter of LE: (0) absent; (1) present.
20. PMEs contiguous (separated by their diameter or less): (0) absent; (1) present. This character is important for distinguishing between Palpimanidae genera (Platnick 1975).
21. Tapetum: (0) primitive; (1) canoe-shaped; (2) grate-shaped; (3) absent. This character is based on character 47 of Griswold et al (2005), which codes palpimanoids as having a canoe-shaped tapetum. However, we score extant palpimanoids as 'primitive' due to lack of a central, dark line that bisects two shiny parts. This character is only observable in extant specimens.
22. PME shape: (0) round; (1) elongated.
23. PME size relative to LE size: (0) same size as LEs; (1) larger than LEs.
24. If PME larger than LE, at least three times as large: (0) absent; (1) present. The eyes of Lagonomegopidae and Lycosidae are dramatically large.
25. PMEs positioned on lateral-anterior edge of carapace: (0) absent; (1) present. This character defines Lagonomegopidae (Guo et al. 2021).
26. Carapace/chelicerae texture: (0) smooth; (1) scales and/or tubercles. Carapace texture was defined as either smooth, as in most of the non-palpimanoid outgroups in the study, or having scales and/or tubercles. Palpimanoids can have either scales, tubercles, or a mixture

of both. In palpimanoids this is sometimes observed as a continuous state, with scales graduating into tubercles. This character examines the texture on the main portion of carapace and not on the lateral edges. The carapace is missing from the fossil *Myrmecarchaea* sp. from Indian Cambay amber (BSIP-41985), so this character was scored based on the texture of the sternum.

27. If state 1 was selected for character 26, large tubercles present only on lateral edges of carapace: (0) absent; (1) present.
28. If state 1 was selected for character 26, carapace/chelicerae texture with scales: (0) absent; (1) present.
29. If state 1 was selected for character 26, carapace/chelicerae texture bumpy or tuberculate: (0) absent; (1) present.
30. If present was selected for character 29, size of tubercles: (0) large tubercles present, typically at base of setae (and finer scale small bumps may also be present); (1) only finer scale small bumps, no large tubercles.
31. If present was selected for character 29, tubercles only present around “neck” area, posterior to chelicerae: (0) absent; (1) present. This character is only present in *Mecymauchenius segmentatus*, but has been observed in other mecymaucheniiids not included in this study.
32. Presence of feathery setae anywhere on body: (0) absent; (1) present. Feathery setae are defined as plumose setae that are flattened with prongs on lateral sides, like a feather. This character was coded as ‘present’ in *Stegodyphus* and *Lineaburmops*.

33. Density of plumose seta on carapace/chelicerae: (0) sparsely ciliate; (1) thick and densely plumose. All taxa in the study had plumose hairs, but in some taxa there were spaces between individual cilia, and in others the cilia were closely packed.
34. Shape of plumose seta on carapace/chelicerae: (0) seta is thicker at base and tapers off toward distal tip; (1) seta is same width throughout and blunt at tip. This character examines whether the shape of plumose setae is blunt or tapering. Archaeidae have plumose carapace setae that is blunt at the tip, although this character was often difficult to discern in fossil archaeid specimens.
35. Presence of branching rows of setae on tubercles: (0) absent; (1) present. Branching rows are only seen in Archaeidae and is particularly prominent on the “neck” and the portion of carapace close to the coxae.
36. Three parallel rows of setae on the ocular/cephalic area of carapace, that run antero-posterior: (0) absent; (1) present. Fossil specimen *Pekkachilus vesica*, F2923, only had two rows but was still scored as ‘present’.
37. If present, length of setae: (0) short to long; (1) dramatically long. *Micropalpimanus* and Palpimanidae fossil specimen F2958 had remarkably long setae on the cephalic area of the carapace.
38. Fovea: (0) absent; (1) present.
39. If fovea present, the shape is a short or long straight seam that runs anteroposterior: (0) absent; (1) present.
40. If present for character 39, seam length: (0) short; (1) long.

41. If fovea present, shape is pit, or variation of a pit: (0) absent; (1) present. Fovea shape can be a rounded pit, 'u' shaped, 'v' shaped, upside-down raindrop, etc. Fovea shape was broken into several characters because some taxa had both a pitted shape and a seam.
42. If present for 41: (0) rounded pit; (1) 'v' or 'u' shaped, or upside-down triangle or tear.
43. Tubercle modification at posterior edge of sternum: (0) absent; (1) present.
44. If present, shape of modification: (0) large wide mound; (1) one tubercle; (2) two tubercles. Extant archaeids have a one large tubercle at the posterior edge of the sternum that may be a part of an abdominal stridulatory system. Some palpimanids have two tubercles and extant mecysmaucheniids have a large mound.
45. Sternum/coxae interlock points on coxae 3 and 4 are larger than on coxae 1 and 2, and curve to the posterior: (0) absent; (1) present.
46. Anterior coxae pointed rather than curved: (0) absent; (1) present.
47. Sternum fused to intercoxal/pleural sclerites: (0) absent; (1) present.
48. Posterior edge of sternum fused to pedicle: (0) absent; (1) present.
49. Sternum shape: (0) sternum shield-shaped, that is, widest between legs 1 and 2 so that sternum between coxae 4 is less than or equal to 1/2 sternum length between coxae; (1) narrow; (2) oval-shaped, sternum widest between legs 2 and 3.
50. Lateral spur on each side of pedicle: (0) absent; (1) present. This character is present only in *Myrmecarchaea*. Only sclerotized spurs were scored present, for example, there seemed to be membraneous lateral bulges in *Pekkachilus vesica* F292, but this was scored as absent.

51. Elongation of the pedicle: (0) absent; (1) present. This character was present only in some *Myrmecarchaea* and some Vetiatoriidae specimens. For the vetiatoriids, it was unclear whether the long pedicle was an artifact of fossil preservation.
52. If present was selected for character 51, pedicle extremely elongated, three times as long as wide: (0) absent; (1) present.
53. Posterior of carapace elongated so that there is a space between coxae 3 and 4 (there may also be an elongation between coxae 2 and 3) that is larger than the space between coxae 1 and 2: (0) absent; (1) present. This character is only present in some *Myrmecarchaea*.
54. Chillum: (0) absent; (1) present.
55. If present, chillum shape: (0) divided, bilateral; (1) single, medial.
56. Shape of inter-cheliceral-sclerite between cheliceral bases: (0) rod; (1) internal structure not visible on exterior; (2) reduced, squat shape, not elongated. Computed tomography scans of extant archaeids revealed that the inter-cheliceral-sclerite is internal and not visible on the cuticle (Wood and Parkinson 2019). In archaeid fossil specimens with the inter-cheliceral area visible, this structure was not seen, and it was assumed the structure was internal rather than absent.
57. If rod-shaped, with four lateral projections, two anterior and two posterior: (0) absent; (1) present.
58. Sclerites directly beneath inter-cheliceral-sclerite: (0) absent; (1) present.
59. If present, shape of most anterior sclerite: (0) triangular; (1) bar. Archaeids have a triangular sclerite and other palpimanoids have a bar that runs from one edge of the carapace to the other side, creating a foramen around the cheliceral bases.

60. If bar present, shape: (0) wider bar running across, but split and not fused in the middle; (1) long, narrow bar, fused in the middle.
61. If present for character 59, presence of a second sclerite posterior to first sclerite: (0) absent; (1) present.
62. If present for character 61, shape of second sclerite: (0) small reduced bar; (1) large bar running across but split in the middle. Archaeids have a small reduced bar that sits under and is only as wide as the triangular sclerite.
63. Clypeal hood – anterior edge of carapace is triangular: (0) absent; (1) present.
64. Lateral labral spurs: (0) absent; (1) present, sclerotized; (2) present, but reduced and membranous.
65. Labrum pointed at tip and pointing more anterior than endites: (0) absent; (1) present. This trait is only observed in *Huttonia*.
66. Shape of distal edge of labium: (0) straight to rounded; (1) narrow, v-shaped notch; (2) shallow, wide notch; (3) pointed.
67. Labium fused to sternum: (0) absent; (1) present.
68. Endite shape: (0) basally parallel, distally convergent, blunt at tip; (1) triangular, convergent along entire inner margin; (2) equant, not meeting above labium.
69. Endite tall and boxy, that is, height in lateral view at least 75% of chelicerae length: (0) absent; (1) present.
70. Posterior dorsal edge of pedicel with two internal elongations: (0) absent; (1) present. Present in palpimanids and *Colopea*.
71. Carapace shape: (0) round back, narrow in front, shaped like a Lycosidae; (1) oval in dorsal view, smoothly rounded, smoothly humped in lateral view; (2) cephalic area boxy, shaped

like a Salticidae; (3) diamond shaped in dorsal view – there may be some elevation or extension of the cephalic area, but not a tubular “neck”; (4) cephalic area elevated and distinct, but carapace does not form tubular “neck”; (5) carapace elevated forming a tubular “neck” and foramen encircling cheliceral bases. Huttonids have a very oval carapace – the anterior is narrower than the posterior, but the overall shape is very smooth.

72. If carapace has a tubular “neck”: (0) “neck” cylindrical; (1) “neck” constricted, forming a distinct “head” region.
73. If carapace has a tubular “neck”, carapace height is more than twice carapace length: (0) absent; (1) present.
74. If carapace has a tubular “neck”, shape of “neck” seam posterior to chelicerae: (0) seam absent, not completely fused; (1) seam smooth; (2) seam rebordered, that is, with thickened edges.
75. Lateral anterior edges of carapace have rectangular, reinforced corners, that project forward, and there is an indentation/invagination on the carapace area beneath the AMEs in the lateral view: (0) absent; (1) present. This trait is observed in fossil specimens that are closely related to the extant mecysmaucheniids.
76. Carapace lateral edge undulates around the coxae: (0) absent; (1) present. This character was present in most Vetiatoridae specimens and also in Stenochilidae.
77. If present, undulations large or reduced: (0) large; (1) reduced.
78. Cephalic area backward or forward tilting, diagnosed based on whether the eyes and cheliceral bases are anterior to the endites in the lateral view: (0) eyes and cheliceral bases posterior to or directly above endites; (1) eyes and cheliceral bases are extended anterior past the endites.

79. In lateral view, cephalic area elevated above eyes: (0) absent; (1) present. The presence of this character has only been observed in Archaeidae. This character is useful for distinguishing between fossil specimens related to archaeids versus those related to mecysmaucheniids. However, it should be noted that some *Myrmecarchaea* and *Eoarchaea* lack this trait.
80. If present, position of elevation: (0) elevated mound maximum height at posterior of “head”; (1) elevated “head” mound maximum height more anterior, close to PME. In archaeids from Burmese amber the elevated “head” mound is more anterior than in other archaeids.
81. Endite length: (0) less than half the carapace length; (1) at least half the carapace length. When the carapace is modified into a tubular “neck”, the carapace length is measured in the lateral view from the carapace edge just above the endites to the posterior edge of the carapace.
82. Endites orientation in lateral view: (0) pointing forward, above the coxae in the lateral view; (1) pointing at least 45° downward, lower than coxae in lateral view.
83. Shape of carapace posterior: (0) smoothly tapering off ; (1) truncated.
84. Carapace posterior with narrow tubular elongation preceding the pedicle: (0) absent; (1) present.
85. If present, with an invagination around the pedicle: (0) absent; (1) present.
86. Size of intercoxal sclerites: (0) large, filling up majority of intercoxal space; (1) reduced, so that the majority of intercoxal space is membranous.

Legs

87. Dorsal, basal portion of tarsus I: (0) similar to rest of segment; (1) modification present.
88. If present, shape of tarsus I modification: (0) large bulge (may be membranous) with foldings; (1) membranous ring around tarsus. This character was difficult to score in fossil taxa and was scored as '1' if there was a basal cuticular constriction in tarsus I.
89. Patella with retrolateral bulge: (0) absent; (1) present. In *Archaea paradoxa*, this character was scored as 'present' even though it is reduced in size and only on patella III and IV.
90. A retrolateral, basal, thin, membranous groove on patella: (0) present; (1) absent. This groove may also be preceded by a large notch at the retrolateral, basal edge, but this character is only scored 'present' if there is a long, thin groove. This groove extends at least 1/3 of the patella length.
91. Tubercles on leg I: (0) absent; (1) present.
92. If present, differences in males and females: (0) present in both sexes; (1) present only in males. If only one sex is known, then this character is scored as 'unknown'.
93. Leg III metatarsus apical, ventral, modified setae (preening comb): (0) absent; (1) present.
94. If present, shape of modified setae: (0) thick brush extending along ventral of metatarsus; (1) straight, single row of modified setae at distal, ventral edge of metatarsus; (2) spines. For *Lineaburmops* sp., the male (*L. maculatus*) had spines and the female (sp. indet.) had a brush of hairs, and this taxon was scored as '0' based on the female.
95. Tarsal organ: (0) exposed; (1) capsulate. This character could only be scored in extant taxa.
96. If exposed, shape of tarsal organ: (0) flat plate; (1) with elongated sensilla.
97. Femur IV curved: (0) straight or with slight curve; (1) with distinct curve.

98. Tibia 1 curved: (0) absent - straight; (1) present. This character was observed in some Palpimanidae and relatives. This character can be difficult to distinguish as there may only be minor bending observed in the dorsal edge.
99. Dorsal surface of femora with a bump: (0) absent – smooth; (1) present. Some taxa have basally enlarged femora, such as palpimanids, but this character was only scored as present if, regardless of femora enlargement, there was a small bump present.
100. Scopulae on leg I: (0) absent; (1) present.
101. If present, relative length of scopulae stalk to spatulate tip: (0) spatulate tip elongated – stalk length approximately equal to spatulate tip length; (1) stalk proportionally longer – about four to six times as long as spatulate tip.
102. If present, scopulae stalk form: (0) ciliate; (1) smooth.
103. If present, shape of scopulae patch: (0) large group; (1) narrow row.
104. If present, scopulae occurring primarily on prolateral of leg I (and can also include a separate patch on retrolateral): (0) absent – scopulae primarily on ventral side; (1) present.
105. If present for 104, scopulae in two separate patches, one on prolateral and one on retrolateral or ventral: (0) absent – only on prolateral; (1) present.
106. Scopulae on leg II: (0) absent; (1) present.
107. Leg IV patella and tibia joint hyperextended due to basal bend in tibia: (0) absent – straight; (1) present.
108. Femur I thicker (more robust) than femur III or IV: (0) absent; (1) present. Present in most palpimanoids except extant Mecysmaucheniids (and closely related fossil lineages).

109. If present, femur II also thicker than femur III or IV: (0) absent; (1) present. Some palpimanoids have only the first pair of legs thickened, but other lineages have both anterior pairs equally more robust than the posterior legs.
110. If present, width of femur I compared to posterior femurs: (0) 1.5–2 times as thick; (1) 2.5–3 times as thick. Leg I of palpimanids are markedly more robust compared to other palpimanoids.
111. Leg length, femur I is at least twice as long as the carapace length: (0) absent - less than or equal to; (1) present. When the carapace is modified into a tubular “neck”, the carapace length is measured in the lateral view from the carapace edge just above the endites to the posterior edge of the carapace.
112. If present, femur I at least four times as long as carapace length: (0) absent; (1) present. Some fossil lineages have all legs exceptionally long. The extant archæid *Eriauchenius workmani* was scored as ‘present’, but unlike in the fossils, it is only the first legs that are exceptionally long.
113. Leg III length: (0) femur III about 50-75% of femur I length; (1) femur III less than half the length of femur I.
114. Leg IV length: (0) femur IV shorter than femur I; (1) femur IV equal to or shorter than femur I.
115. Tibia I in males with a ventral invagination: (0) absent; (1) present. Only present in *Palpimanus*, possibly for clasping during mating.
116. Relative length of patella I and tarsus I: (0) patella shorter than tarsus; (1) patella longer than or equal to tarsus.

117. If present, patella I at least twice as long as tarsus I: (0) absent; (1) present. Some palpimanids have unusually long patella relative to the tarsus.
118. Tarsus 1 with a blunt tip: (0) absent; (1) present. In extant palpimanids, tarsus I does not gradually taper off, but is more truncated.
119. Tarsi I and II bulging ventrally: (0) absent; (1) present. Only present in *Colopea* sp.
120. Superior tarsal claws I smaller than STC IV (or III): (0) absent; (1) present.
121. STC I with teeth longer and more comb-like compared to STC IV (or III): (0) absent; (1) present.
122. Tarsal claws: (0) two; (1) three.
123. Reduced teeth on claws: (0) absent; (1) present.
124. Inferior claw IV thick and short versus long and thin: (0) short, thick; (1) long, thin.
125. Inferior claw IV: (0) present; (1) absent.
126. Claw tufts: (0) absent; (1) present.
127. Trochanter distal margin: (0) entire; (1) notched.
128. Tarsal trichobothria: (0) absent; (1) present.
129. If present, tarsal trichobothria rows: (0) one row; (1) two or more.
130. Metatarsal trichobothria: (0) one; (1) two; (2) three or more.
131. If one trichobothria present, metatarsal placement: (0) distal 1/3 of metatarsus; (1) middle 1/3 of metatarsus.
132. Serrate accessory claw setae: (0) absent; (1) present.
133. Leg cuticle texture: (0) smooth; (1) scales and/or bumpy. This character deals with the texture visible using a light microscope and not the fine-scale texture visible using a

scanning electron microscope. Palpimanids have ‘smooth’ legs. Other palpimanoids have either scales, bumps, or a mixture of both, with scales graduating into bumps.

134. If present for scales and/or bumpy, leg texture with scales: (0) absent; (1) present.
135. If present for scales and/or bumpy, leg texture bumpy: (0) absent; (1) present.
136. Trichobothrial base hood and texture: (0) hood absent; (1) smooth or same as leg texture; (2) with transverse ridges.
137. Reduced leg spines: (0) absent – spines scattered on some or all legs; (1) present – either no spines present or reduced spines, consisting of only distal spines on some leg segments.
138. If present for character 137, pattern of spine reduction: (0) no spines present; (1) reduced – distal spines on some leg segments but no pattern; (2) reduced - distal region of tibia III (and maybe tibia IV) with ventral and lateral pair, distal region of metatarsus IV (and maybe metatarsus III) with ventral pair, and patella III with single, distal, prolateral spine.

Chelicerae

139. Chelicerae anterior surface: (0) smooth; (1) with spine or brush of setae.
140. If present, cheliceral modification in females: (0) spine; (1) absent in female; (3) a bump or apophysis. In some fossil taxa there are no female exemplars, and we assumed the male and female look the same, and this character was scored based on the male morphology. In all Palpimanoidea with cheliceral modifications, except *Zephyrarchaea*, the males and females share the same morphology.
141. If present, cheliceral modification in males: (0) same as female; (1) brush of setae.
142. Ridge on lateral anterior edge of chelicerae: (0) absent; (1) present. Present only in extant palpimanids.

143. Basal edge of chelicerae: (0) parallel edge; (1) splayed out. The basal cheliceral edges are fanned out in mecysmaucheniids and archaeids and their fossil relatives. This is determined by examining whether the basal cheliceral edge follows the line of the distal paturon cuticle, or it turns outward.
144. Basal cheliceral constriction where chelicerae contact carapace foramen: (0) absent; (1) present.
145. Cheliceral 'trigger hairs': (0) absent; (1) present. These setae are long and run along the inner margins of the chelicerae. In extant mecysmauchenids, these hairs project anterior when the chelicerae are held open with a wide gape (Wood et al. 2016).
146. Trigger hair distribution: (0) scattered; (1) one evenly spaced row.
147. Trigger hair length: (0) short; (1) long. Short setae would be approximately the width of chelicerae, and long setae would run nearly down to the endites.
148. Peg teeth: (0) absent; (1) present.
149. If present for character 148, peg teeth present on both the retromargin and promargin: (0) absent – only on the promargin; (1) present. This character is diagnosed based on where the fang tip closes on the cheliceral margin and whether peg teeth are posterior to that area or not.
150. If present for character 148, two distinct anterior rows of peg teeth: (0) absent; (1) present. In mecysmaucheniids and archaeids (and their fossil members) there is a distinct second row of peg teeth anterior to the main row that runs along the promargin.
151. If present, number: (0) two peg teeth; (1) more than two. Some palpimanoids have only two peg teeth in this row (Archaeidae, Spatiatoridae, Huttoniidae).

152. If present, main row of peg teeth, closest to fang, that runs along promargin, with reduced density (approximately half the density), peg teeth widely separated: (0) absent; (1) present.
153. If present, peg teeth texture: (0) smooth: (1) textured, with fingerprint ridges. This character is only visible in scanning electron (SEM) images and can only be scored in the extant taxa.
154. If present, promargin row of peg teeth closest to fang has an alternating pattern of long, short, long, short: (0) absent – uniform lengths or length variation is random; (1) present – long, short, long, short pattern.
155. If present for peg teeth, peg teeth shape is blunt at tip (tapering peg teeth may also be present): (0) absent – all peg teeth tapering at tip; (1) present – some or all peg teeth blunt at tip. In some taxa the peg teeth are more seta-like, that is tapering at the tip, opposed to rounded and blunter at the tip. Some taxa have both kinds of peg teeth.
156. If present, most distal peg teeth on promargin tapering and seta-like and graduating to blunt peg teeth more basally (as you move closer to where fang tip closes on paturon cuticle): (0) absent; (1) present.
157. Thickened setae at fang base: (0) absent; (1) present. This character is based on character 34 of Griswold et al (2005).
158. Cheliceral stridulatory striae: (0) absent; (1) present. Palpimanoids have stridulatory ridges on their chelicerae that take the form of dense, closely spaced small ridges, or larger wider-spaced ridges, or both.
159. If present, uniform and densely spaced fingerprint-like ridges in females: (0) absent; (1) present.
160. If present, widely spaced ridges in females: (0) absent; (1) present.

161. If present, uniform and densely spaced fingerprint-like ridges in males: (0) absent; (1) present.
162. If present, widely spaced ridges in males: (0) absent; (1) present.
163. If present, cheliceral stridulatory ridges running parallel to the frontal plane on lateral side of chelicerae, but stridulatory ridges also present on posterior of chelicerae where they turn and then run parallel to the sagittal plane: (0) absent – ridges only present on lateral of chelicera and are parallel to the frontal plane; (1) present.
164. If present, cheliceral stridulatory area with a smooth, distinct edge making the striae patch that is oval-shaped: (0) absent – irregular, uneven edge; (1) present.
165. If present, placement of stridulatory ridge on chelicerae: (0) basal 1/3; (1) middle 1/3; (2) distal 1/3. To score, divide chelicerae length into thirds and score based on the section that contains the majority of the stridulatory ridge.
166. If stridulatory striae present, picks on palpal femur: (0) absent; (1) at least one cusp present. *Madagascarchaea lavatenda* was scored as ‘present’ but picks were only present in the male and not the female.
167. If present, number of cusps: (0) one cusp; (1) more than one.
168. Palpal femur bends around chelicerae: (0) absent – palpal femur straight; (1) present.
169. Distal third of chelicerae curved to the posterior in lateral view: (0) absent – straight or only slightly curved; (1) present.
170. Distal third of chelicerae curved laterad in anterior view: (0) absent; (1) present.
171. In lateral view, a distinct basal bend in the chelicerae: (0) absent; (1) present. This character is only observed in mecysmaucheniids and close fossil relatives.
172. Inward arch (opposite to fang curve) in cheliceral fang margin: (0) absent; (1) present.

173. If present, arched section is greater than 1.5 times the fang length: (0) absent; (1) present.
174. Cheliceral distal tip tapering, that is, less than three times as wide as the basal fang width: (0) absent; (1) present.
175. Cheliceral gland mound: (0) absent; (1) present.
176. If present, placement of gland mound on retromargin: (0) closer to the middle of the retromargin; (1) close to the edge of the retromargin where the fang tip meets the paturon cuticle.
177. If present, gland mound shape: (0) large flat bulge; (1) pointed (in SEM this looks like a reduced tooth on top of the mound); (2) mound longer and thinner than wide; (3) wide, rounded mound,
178. Fang edge serrated: (0) present; (1) absent.
179. Fang shape: (0) evenly curved; (1) more curved close to the tip; (2) less curved, straighter, close to the tip; (3) hook-like, more curved than typical.
180. Distal, posterior paturon cuticle extends more ventrad than the closed fangs: (0) absent; (1) present.
181. A groove or depression where the closed fang meets the paturon cuticle: (0) absent – flat; (1) present – with groove.
182. Cheliceral boss: (0) absent; (1) present. This was scored as ‘present’ for *Stegodyphus*, *Schizocosa*, *Zelotes* and *Lineaburmops*. In *Stegodyphus*, the edge of the carapace is modified to curve around the cheliceral boss and this same carapace modification, as well as the presence of what appears to be a boss, was observed in some Lagonomegopidea specimens.

183. Cheliceral chela: (0) absent; (1) intermediate – with a large tooth that is keel-like, creating a chela; (2) present. *Dysdera* and *Stegodyphus* were scored as ‘intermediate’ because of a large keel-like tooth that seemed like an intermediate chela.
184. Cheliceral basal fusion: (0) free; (1) fused. All taxa in the study scored as ‘free’.

Abdomen

185. Abdomen shape in lateral view, excluding tubercles: (0) smoothly curved, elongate; (1) smoothly curved, semicircle; (2) anterior rounded, posterior flat; (3) anterior flat, posterior rounded.
186. Abdomen anterior extends over the pedicle and carapace posterior: (0) absent; (1) present.
187. Abdomen setae shape: (0) with a long taper, usually seta is thin, but can be thick and densely plumose; (1) club-like, blunt at end, usually thick and densely plumose. Abdomen setae may be thick or thin, but this character looks specifically at whether the tip tapers or is blunt. Most archaeids have blunt, club-like seta on their abdomen, particularly obvious on the posterior above the spinnerets.
188. Large sclerotized pits on abdomen: (0) absent; (1) present.
189. A pair of seta on the anterior of abdomen that project anterior: (0) absent; (1) present. In *Palpimanus* this was only observed in the male, but was scored as ‘present.’
190. Abdomen tubercles: (0) absent; (1) present.
191. If present, placement of abdomen tubercles: (0) only a single tubercle present; (1) pairs of tubercles present, but may also have a singular tubercle as well.
192. Posterior respiratory system: (0) booklungs; (1) tracheae or modifications thereof.

193. Posterior spiracle shape: (0) single; (1) double. Archaeids and some fossil mecysmaucheniids have a double posterior spiracle.
194. Placement of posterior respiratory system: (0) close to epigastric furrow; (1) close to spinnerets.
195. Dorsal abdominal scutum on male that extends to dorsal surface: (0) absent; (1) present.
196. Sclerotization around anterior of abdomen: (0) absent; (1) present.
197. If present, shape of sclerotization: (0) dorsal and ventral sclerotization; (1) only ventral sclerotization.
198. If present, dorsal and ventral plates fused in females: (0) absent – separate; (1) present – fused.
199. If present, dorsal and ventral plates fused in males: (0) absent – separate; (1) present – fused.
200. If present, epigynum fused with booklung covers in females: (0) absent; (1) present.
201. Epiandrous spigots: (0) absent; (1) present.
202. Epiandrous spigot distribution: (0) dispersed; (1) in two bunches.
203. Small sclerites close to and posteriad of epigastric fold: (0) absent; (1) present.
204. Abdomen with distinct folds: (0) absent; (1) present.
205. Spinnerets projected on conical tubercle: (0) absent; (1) present.

Female pedipalp

206. Thick, distinct, brush of seta on prolateral of tarsus: (0) absent; (1) present.
207. Thick, distinct brush of seta on retrolateral side of tarsus: (0) absent; (1) present.
208. Prolateral spines on tarsus: (0) absent; (1) present.

- 209. If present, placement of tarsal spines: (0) scattered; (1) one row.
- 210. Spine/s on distal portion of tibia: (0) absent; (1) present.
- 211. If present, number of spines: (0) one spine; (1) two spines; (2) more than two.
- 212. Spine/s on femur: (0) absent; (1) present.
- 213. If present, number: (0) one spine; (1) several spines.
- 214. Female palp claw: (0) present; (1) absent or very reduced.

Female genitalia

- 215. Female genitalia with fertilization ducts, or for fossils, with external openings on epigynum: (0) haplogyne; (1) entelegyne. This character was scored as ‘unknown’ for *Lineaburmops*.
- 216. Epigynum: (0) absent; (1) present. An epigynum is defined as any sclerotization around the female genitalia (character 130: Griswold et al. 2005). This was scored ‘absent’ for *Dysdera* and *Hickmania* because a distinct, strongly sclerotized plate was not observed. In some palpimanoids there is ventral sclerotized plate that covers the booklungs as well as the epigynum, and this was scored as ‘present’ for an epigynum.
- 217. Presence of a thick, convex ridge on the posterior edge of the epigastric furrow that fits into the anterior edge: (0) absent; (1) present.
- 218. Membranous bursa: (0) absent; (1) present.
- 219. Sclerite on lateral sides of internal genitalia: (0) absent; (1) present.
- 220. If present, lateral sclerites size: (0) small, reduced; (1) elongated.
- 221. Posterior edge of epigynum arched: (0) absent; (1) present.
- 222. Pores on bursa: (0) absent; (1) present.

223. Internal sclerotized plate that is dorsal to the bursa: (0) absent; (1) present. This character refers to the female sclerotized genital plate (FSGP) observed in Wood (2008).
224. FSGP with wing-like structures on lateral sides: (0) absent; (1) present.
225. FSGP with keel-like structure in the middle: (0) absent; (1) present.
226. Sclerotized spermathecae: (0) absent; (1) present.
227. Membranous sacs/spermathecae: (0) absent; (1) present. This study distinguishes between sclerotized and unsclerotized structures. Palpimanoids typically have numerous membranous sacs coming off the bursa, but some palpimanids have both sclerotized and membranous spermathecae. The term ‘spermathecae’ is used here for any invagination of the internal female genitalia and it is unknown whether these structures are homologous across spiders.
228. If present, number of sacs: (0) one per side; (1) two per side; (3) more than two per side. This character does not count the large balloons (character 233, below) seen in some palpimanids.
229. If present, shape of sacs: (0) sacs sessile; (1) sacs on narrow stalks.
230. If present, sacs clustered or dispersed: (0) dispersed; (1) one cluster per side. This character does not include the ‘large balloons’ below (character 233). If there is only one sac per side, is scored as ‘not applicable.’
231. Presence of pores on membranous sacs: (0) absent; (1) present. Scored as ‘present’ for all taxa with membranous sacs, except *Huttonia*.
232. If present, pores have a long tail with a sperm-like shape: (0) absent – various shapes; (1) present – long tail.

233. Two structures that look like balloons, that are membranous, are larger than and occur more medially than the sac-like structure, which often are lateral: (0) absent; (1) present.

This character is present in some palpimanid lineages.

Male secondary genitalia - pedipalps

234. Fusion of tegulum and subtegulum: (0) absent; (1) present.

235. Bulb shape in ventral view: (0) oval; (1) round, as wide as high.

236. Pedipalp trochanters elongate, at least half the length of pedipalp femur: (0) absent; (1) present.

237. Pedipalp femur, patella, and tibia thicker than in female: (0) absent; (1) present.

238. Groove/sulcus on palpal bulb: (0) absent; (1) present.

239. If present, orientation of groove: (0) transverse; (1) in between, 45°; (2) sagittal.

240. Scattered spines on prolateral of cymbium: (0) absent; (1) present.

241. Cluster of long setae on prolateral side of pedipalpal tibia: (0) absent; (1) present.

242. Cymbium shape convex plate: (0) absent – conical shape; (1) present – elongate plate about two times as long as wide. Some cymbium have a narrow elongation at the anterior tip and if present, this elongation is not factored into the length to width ratio.

243. If present for character 242, retrolateral edge of cymbium with broad invagination: (0) absent; (1) present.

244. Cymbium shape with narrow, anterior elongation: (0) absent; (1) present.

245. Trichobothria on pedipalp tibia: (0) one row; (1) two rows; (2) three rows. Rows may have from one to five trichobothria. *Dysdera* has one dorsal, one prolateral and one retrolateral trichobothria and was scored as having three rows.

246. Conductor: (0) absent; (1) present.
247. Conductor shape: (0) conductor separate from embolus; (1) conductor embraces embolus.
248. Embolus with a distinct spiral: (0) absent; (1) present. This character was coded as 'present' in *Archaea paradoxa* and *Myrmecharchaea antecessor*.
249. Median apophysis (MA): (0) absent; (1) present.
250. If present, MA large and pointing postero-retrolateral and posterior: (0) absent; (1) present. This character was only observed in fossil specimens closely related to the extant mecysmaucheniids.
251. Palpal tarsus M30 muscle: (0) absent; (1) present. M30 and M29, below, were scored based on Huber (2004), but this study used a different genus of Eresidae, Gnaphosidae, and Lycosidae than our study. The current study assumes that this character is the same for all genera within a family, and scored these families as 'present', but this may not be the case.
252. Palpal tarsus M29 muscle: (0) absent; (1) present.
253. Retrolateral apophysis on femur: (0) absent; (1) present.
254. Retrolateral apophysis on patella: (0) absent; (1) present.
255. Modification on tibia: (0) absent; (1) present.
256. If present, shape of modification: (0) retrolateral apophysis; (1) ventral apophysis; (2) retrolateral modification involving setae. This character attempts to categorize modifications of the tibia based on likely homologies due to position (retrolateral or ventral) and due to structure (presence of modified seta or a cuticular apophysis).
257. If setal tibia modification present, shape: (0) one or more short, thick seta not on protrusion; (1) one thick seta on a protrusion.
258. Cymbium with an apophysis with a thick, short spine on top: (0) absent; (1) present.

259. Pedipalp bulb apex with a dark ridge spiraling around to form conductor: (0) absent; (1) present.
260. Pedipalpal bulb greatly expands in embolus area: (0) absent; (1) present. This character has been observed in palpimanoids (Rix and Harvey 2011, 2012a, b, Wood and Scharff 2018, Rix et al. 2021)

Spinnerets

261. Posterior spinnerets reduced: (0) absent - PMS developed, PLS as long as ALS; (1) present – very reduced or gone with only spigots remaining.
262. If PLS unreduced, PLS tip rounded: (0) absent; (1) present.
263. Spigot base texture: (0) fingerprint texture; (1) smooth.
264. Cribellum: (0) absent; (1) present.
265. Cribellum organization: (0) entire; (1) divided.
266. Cribellate spigots: (0) strobilate; (1) claviform.
267. PMS paracribellar gland spigots in females: (0) absent; (1) present.
268. PMS paracribellar gland spigots in male: (0) absent; (1) present.
269. PLS paracribellar gland spigots in females: (0) absent; (1) present.
270. PLS modified spigot: (0) absent; (1) present.
271. ALS MAP field separated by furrow: (0) absent; (1) present.
272. ALS segment number: (0) three; (1) two.
273. Tartipores: (0) absent; (1) present.
274. PMS mAP position: (0) median to anterior; (1) posterior: (2) absent.
275. Cylindrical gland spigots: (0) absent; (1) present.

Appendix 2: Additional Phylogenetic Results

The parsimony search using the morphology-only dataset found 450,000 trees of length 929, with the first tree having a consistency index (CI) of 0.323, a retention index (RI) of 0.761 and a rescaled consistency index (RC) of 0.246. The parsimony search of the 50% and 70% occupancy molecular-only datasets recovered two trees of length 40,745, and one tree of length 13,700, respectively. The Total Evidence parsimony analyses recovered 238,000 trees of length 41,727, and 208,000 trees of length 14,671 with the 50% and 70% molecular datasets respectively.

The phylogenetic analyses of the molecular data at 50% and 70% occupancies (Figs. S3-S6) failed to recover a well-supported, monophyletic Palpimanoidea. Instead, the Parsimony analysis of the 50% dataset recovered Palpimanidae + the entelegyne taxa + *Hickmania*, but only with 59% bootstrap (bs) support. The Likelihood analysis of the 50% dataset recovered the Palpimanidae as sister to the entelegynes + *Hickmania*, in this case with 88% and 80% Shimodaira–Hasegawa–like likelihood ratio test (SH-*alrt*) and Ultrafast Bootstrap (UFBoot) support, respectively. These same relationships were recovered in the 70% dataset but these nodes had less than 50% branch support. In all analyses, those families with multiple genera (Archaeidae, Mecysmaucheniidae, and Palpimanidae) were recovered with 100% branch support.

The phylogenetic analysis of the morphological dataset (Figs. S1-S2), which includes fossil taxa, recovered a monophyletic Palpimanoidea (70% bs, 94% SH, 98% UFBoot), except with †Lagonomegopidae falling outside and with the entelegyne taxa. Extant families and their stem fossils were strongly supported as monophyletic, with some fossil taxa currently considered Archaeidae falling instead as stem Mecysmaucheniidae, justifying taxonomic transfer.

Archaeidae + Mecysmaucheniidae (including their fossil relatives and †Planarchaeidae) formed a well-supported monophyletic group in the Likelihood analysis (95% SH-ahrt, 78% UFBoot), called here the “high-carapace” clade. This relationship was recovered in the strict-consensus phylogeny resulting from the Parsimony analysis, but had less than 50% bs. Most of the remaining palpimanoids formed a monophyletic group called here the “low-carapace clade” (71% bs, 99% SH-ahrt, 100% UFBoot). †*Seppo*, †*Onychopalpus*, and †*Sinaranea*, some of the oldest Palpimanoidea fossils, fell as the earliest diverging lineages in the Likelihood analysis, and fell as the earliest diverging lineage of the “low-carapace” clade in the Parsimony analysis (< 50% bs). Within the “low carapace” clade, in the Likelihood analysis Palpimanidae plus †*Cretapalpus* diverged first, followed by a paraphyletic †Spatiatoridae (99% SH-ahrt, 88% UFBoot), then a group containing †Micropalpimanidae plus Huttoniidae (59% SH-ahrt, 43% UFBoot), and a group containing a paraphyletic †Vetiatoridae, with Stenochilidae nested within (94% SH-ahrt, 91% UFBoot). In the Parsimony analysis, relationships among the “low carapace” families had bs < 50%. Outside of Palpimanoidea, *Stegodyphus*, *Schizocosa*, *Zelotes*, and †*Lineaburmops* formed a monophyletic group (60% bs, 64% SH-ahrt, 93% UFBoot), and *Hickmania* was sister to this group with 61% SH-ahrt and 84% UFBoot in the Likelihood analysis.

In the Total Evidence analyses (Figs. S7-S10), Palpimanoidea was recovered as monophyletic in the Likelihood TE analysis using the 70% occupancy sequence data (84% SH-ahrt, 97% UFBoot), with †Lagonomegopidae falling with the entelegyne taxa. In the Likelihood TE analysis with the 50% occupancy sequence data Palpimanoidea was not recovered, but alternate relationships had poor branch support: Palpimanidae (plus †*Cretapalpus*) diverged first, followed by a group containing *Hickmania* and the entelegyne taxa (0% SH-ahrt, 40% UFBoot),

and then the remaining Palpimanoidea (60% SH-rlrt, 40% UFBoot). The Parsimony TE with the 70% occupancy sequence data recovered a monophyletic Palpimanoidea in the strict consensus phylogeny, although with < 50% bs support. In the Parsimony, TE with the 50% occupancy data, Palpimanidae fell in a group containing *Hickmania* and the entelegyne taxa, but with < 50% bs support. All families (and their close fossil relatives) were recovered as monophyletic, albeit sometimes with weak branch support, particularly in the Parsimony analysis, with the exception of the following: in all TE analyses †Vetiatoridae was recovered as polyphyletic, with Stenochilidae nested within and with †*Praetervetiator* falling as sister to the extant Mecysmaucheniidae; †*Palaeozearchaea*, currently considered Mecysmaucheniidae, was recovered within the clade containing †Vetiatoridae and Stenochilidae; in the TE analysis using the 70% occupancy molecular data, †Spatiatoridae was paraphyletic, although with weak support. Regarding relationships among the major palpimanoid clades (i.e., families and their closest fossil relatives), Parsimony TE analysis failed to recover any intrafamily relationships with > 50% bs. In the Likelihood TE analysis that used the 50% occupancy data, there was strong support for Archaeidae and its fossil relatives being sister to a group containing these two clades: 1) (Stenochilidae + †Vetiatoridae) and (Huttoniidae + †Micropalpimanidae + †Spatiatoridae); 2) Mecysmaucheniidae and its close fossil relatives, including †Planarchaeidae. In the Likelihood TE analysis that used the 70% occupancy data, the following relationships were strongly to moderately supported: Palpimanidae + †*Cretapalpus* diverged first, followed by a group containing Huttoniidae, †Spatiatoridae, †Micropalpimanidae, †Vetiatoridae, and Stenochilidae, which was sister to a group containing Archaeidae + Mecysmaucheniidae and †Planarchaeidae (the “high-carapace” clade). In all TE analyses, some fossils that are currently considered Archaeidae, fell as stem Mecysmaucheniidae.

Table S1.

Table S1. A list of extant voucher taxa used for morphology. Abbreviations: F = female; M = Male; CASENT = Department of Entomology, California Academy of Sciences; FM = Field Museum; USNMMENT = Entomology Department, National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution. ATOL refers to the image database from the Assembling the Tree of Life - Phylogeny of Spiders project (NSF EAR-0228699), images under Creative Commons -- Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 3.0 United States (CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 US), image author listed in the Acknowledgements.

Family	Species	Country	Voucher	Source of additional images or data
Dysderidae	<i>Dysdera crocata</i>	USA	F: USNMMENT01580345; M: USNMMENT01580350	ATOL
Eresidae	<i>Stegodyphus sp.</i>	Myanmar	F & M: USNMMENT01580361	ATOL
Lycosidae	<i>Schizocosa ocreata</i>	USA	F: USNMMENT01580346; M: USNMMENT01580362	Azevedo et al, 2022
Gnaphosidae	<i>Zelotes duplex</i>	USA	F & M: USNMMENT01580356	Azevedo et al, 2022
Gradungulidae	<i>Hickmania troglodytes</i>	Australia: Tasmania	F: CASENT9020543	Griswold et al, 2005; ATOL
Palpimanidae	<i>Palpimanus capensis</i>	South Africa	F & M: CASENT9070133	ATOL
Palpimanidae	<i>Diaphoracellus isalo</i>	Madagascar	F & M: CASENT9012161	
Palpimanidae	<i>Sceliocteus sp.</i>	Uganda	F & M: CASENT9065042	ATOL
Palpimanidae	<i>Notiothops campana</i>	Chile	F & M: CASENT9053299	Forster & Platnick, 1984
Palpimanidae	<i>Otiothops whitticki</i>	Guyana	F & M: CASENT9070107	ATOL
Stenochilidae	<i>Stenochilus hobsoni</i>	India	F & M: CASENT9023951	Forster & Platnick, 1984
Stenochilidae	<i>Colopea unifoveata</i>	Brunei	F: CASENT9028424; M: CASENT9035143	ATOL
Huttoniidae	<i>Huttonia sp.</i>	New Zealand	F: FM-2005-098; M: FM-2005-086	
Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Aotearoa magna</i>	New Zealand	F & M: CASENT9028269	
Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Zearchaea sp.</i>	New Zealand	F & M: CASENT9028257	
Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Mecysmaucheniis segmentatus</i>	Chile	F & M: CASENT9035498	
Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Mesarchaea bellavista</i>	Chile	M: CASENT9019105	
Archaeidae	<i>Zephyrarchaea mainae</i>	Australia	F: CASENT9028361; M: CASENT9028430	
Archaeidae	<i>Afrarchaea woodae</i>	South Africa	F & M: CASENT9018995	
Archaeidae	<i>Madagascarchaea lavatenda</i>	Madagascar	F & M: CASENT901731	
Archaeidae	<i>Eriachenius workmani</i>	Madagascar	F: CASENT9012335; M: CASENT9028409	

Table S2.

Table S2. Voucher information for molecular sequence data.					
Family	Species	Country	NCBI	UCE Loci recovered	Publication
Dysderidae	<i>Dysdera crocata</i>	USA	SRR11292755	457	Ramírez et al, 2021
Eresidae	<i>Stegodyphus sp.</i>	South Africa	SRR7363157	682	Wood et al, 2018
Lycosidae	<i>Schizocosa rovneri</i>	USA	SRR1514894	297	Bond et al, 2014
Gnaphosidae	<i>Zelotes fratris</i>	USA	SRR16201449	82	Azevedo et al, 2022
Gradungulidae	<i>Hickmania troglodytes</i>	Australia: Tasmania	SRR7363164	313	Wood et al, 2018
Palpimanidae	<i>Palpimanus capensis</i>	South Africa	SRR7363150	300	Wood et al, 2018
Palpimanidae	<i>Diaphoracellus isalo</i>	Madagascar	SRR7363142	335	Wood et al, 2018
Palpimanidae	<i>Scelidocteus sp.</i>	Uganda	SRR7363173	276	Wood et al, 2018
Palpimanidae	<i>Notiothops campana</i>	Chile	SRR7363148	344	Wood et al, 2018
Palpimanidae	<i>Otiothops cf. walckenaeri</i>	French Guiana	SRR7363147	194	Wood et al, 2018
Stenochilidae	<i>Colopea unifoveata</i>	Brunei	SRR7363184	241	Wood et al, 2018
Huttoniidae	<i>Huttonia sp.</i>	New Zealand	SRR7363186	432	Wood et al, 2018
Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Aotearoa magna</i>	New Zealand	SRR7363182	270	Wood et al, 2018
Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Zearchaea fiordensis</i>	New Zealand	SRR7363179	269	Wood et al, 2018
Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Mecysmauchenius segmentatus</i>	Chile	SRR7363178	109	Wood et al, 2018
Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Mesarchaea bellavista</i>	Chile	SRR7363180	317	Wood et al, 2018
Archaeidae	<i>Zephyrarchaea mainae</i>	Australia	SRR7363154	160	Wood et al, 2018
Archaeidae	<i>Afrarchaea woodae</i>	South Africa	SRR7363160	305	Wood et al, 2018
Archaeidae	<i>Madagascarchaea legendrei</i>	Madagascar	SRR7363152	420	Wood et al, 2018
Archaeidae	<i>Eriauchenius andrianampoinimerina</i>	Madagascar	SRR7363185	384	Wood et al, 2018

Table S3.

Table S3: Fossil species voucher information for morphological data. The voucher number is listed for those specimens that were physically examined and the literature citation for when a fossil specimen was coded from the literature. Undetermined taxa, marked with an asterisk (*), were removed from the divergence dating analysis. Institution abbreviations: AMNH = American Museum of Natural History; BSIP = Birbal Sahni Institute for Palaeosciences; GPI = Geologisch-Paläontologisches Institut der Universität Hamburg; MBA = Museum für Naturkunde Berlin, Paläontologisches; SMF = Senckenberg Museum, Frankfurt; SMNG = Senckenberg Museum, Görlitz section; F = J. Wunderlich, private collection; USNMPAL = US National Museum, Smithsonian, Dept. of Paleobiology.

Family	New determination based on examination	Voucher number or Literature citation	Original identification listed for specimen	Sex	Fossil deposit	Holotype
Lagonomegopidae	<i>Lineaburmops</i> sp.					
		F3147	<i>Lineaburmops</i> sp.	F	Burmese amber	
		F2929	<i>Lineaburmops maculatus</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
Palpimanidae	<i>Cretalpalpus vittari</i>					
		Downen & Selden, 2021	<i>Cretalpalpus vittari</i>	F	Crato Formation	X
Palpimanidae	<i>Otiothops</i> sp.					
		SMF-Be-1018	<i>Otiothops</i> sp1	F or juv.	Dominican amber	
		SMF-Be-1026	<i>Otiothops</i> sp1	F or juv.	Dominican amber	
Palpimanidae	New Genus					
		SMF-Be-1034	<i>Otiothops</i> sp2	F	Dominican amber	
Micropalpimanidae	<i>Micropalpimanus poinari</i>					
		F2511	<i>Micropalpimanus poinari</i>	M	Burmese amber	
		F3405	Archaeidae, indet.	M	Burmese amber	
		F2871	<i>Micropalpimanus poinari</i>	F	Burmese amber	
		F3403	Vetiatoridae, indet.	M	Burmese amber	
		F2020	<i>Micropalpimanus poinari</i>	M	Burmese amber	
		F2927	<i>Micropalpimanus poinari</i>	M	Burmese amber	
		F3411	Micropalpimanidae?	M	Burmese amber	
	likely <i>Micropalpimanus</i>	F2958	Palpimanidae sp, indet.	F	Burmese amber	
		F2512	<i>Micropalpimanus poinari</i>	M	Burmese amber	
Micropalpimanidae	<i>Micropalpimanus gibber</i>					
		F3649	<i>Micropalpimanus gibber</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
Vetiatoridae	indet.*					
		F2285	Micropalpimanus, indet.	F	Burmese amber	
Vetiatoridae	indet.*					
		F3410	Palpimanoidea, indet.	M	Burmese amber	
Vetiatoridae	<i>Pekkachilus vesica</i>					
		F2923	<i>Pekkachilus vesica</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
Vetiatoridae	<i>Pekkachilus</i> new species					
		F2953	<i>Pekkachilus</i> , indet.	M	Burmese amber	
		F3053	<i>Pekkachilus</i> , indet.	F	Burmese amber	
Vetiatoridae	<i>Vetiator gracilipes</i>					
		F2954	<i>Vetiator gracilipes</i>	M	Burmese amber	
		F2739	<i>Vetiator gracilipes</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
Spatiatoridae	<i>Spatiator putescens</i>					
		F2740	<i>Spatiator putescens</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
		F3404	Spatiatoridae, indet.	F	Burmese amber	
		F2922	Spatiatoridae, indet.	M	Burmese amber	
Spatiatoridae	<i>Spatiator caulis</i>					
		F2230	<i>Spatiator caulis</i>	M	Baltic amber	X
		F2231	<i>Spatiator</i> , indet. probably <i>caulis</i>	M	Baltic amber	
		SMF-Be-1162	<i>Spatiator</i> , indet.	F	Baltic amber	
Spatiatoridae	<i>Spatiator bitterfeldensis</i>					
		F2864	<i>Spatiator bitterfeldensis</i>	M	Bitterfeld amber	X
Spatiatoridae	<i>Spatiator martensi</i>					
		SMF-Be-1484	<i>Spatiator martensi</i>	M	Baltic amber	X
Huttoniidae	Huttoniidae, indet.					
		F2464	Huttoniidae, prob. Micropalpimanidae	F	New Jersey amber	
Huttoniidae	Huttoniidae, indet.					
		Penny & Selden, 2006	Huttoniidae, indet.	juv.	Grassy Lake amber	
near Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Burmesarchaea quadrata</i>					
		F3013	<i>Burmesarchaea quadrata</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
near Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Burmesarchaea speciosus</i>					
		F1923	<i>Burmesarchaea speciosus</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
near Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Burmesarchaea crassicaput</i>					
		F2949	<i>Burmesarchaea crassicaput</i>	F	Burmese amber	X
near Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Burmesarchaea alissa</i>					
		F2947	<i>Burmesarchaea alissa</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
near Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Burmesarchaea propinqua</i>					
		F2948	<i>Burmesarchaea propinqua</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
near Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Burmesarchaea crassichelae</i>					
		F3068	<i>Burmesarchaea crassichelae</i>	M	Burmese amber	X

Table S3 continued.

near Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Burmesarchaea</i> , indet.*					
		F2627	<i>Burmesarchaea</i> , indet.	F	Burmese amber	
near Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Burmesarchaea longicollum</i>					
		F2950	<i>Burmesarchaea longicollum</i>	F	Burmese amber	X
near Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Burmesarchaea bilongapophyses</i>					
		F3553	<i>Burmesarchaea bilongapophyses</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
near Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Palaeozearchaea depressa</i>					
		F3639	<i>Palaeozearchaea depressa</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
near Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Procervetiator fruticosus</i>					
		F3636	<i>Procervetiator fruticosus</i>	F	Burmese amber	X
near Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Praetervetiator circulus</i>					
		F3568	<i>Praetervetiator circulus</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
near Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Praetervetiator parvicirculus</i>					
		F3689	<i>Praetervetiator parvicirculus</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
near Mecysmaucheniidae	<i>Spiniarchaea aberraus</i>					
		F3610	<i>Spiniarchaea aberraus</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
Planarchaeidae	<i>Eomysmauchenius septentrionalis</i>					
		F1837	<i>Eomysmauchenius septentrionalis</i>	F	Burmese amber	X
Planarchaeidae	<i>Eomysmauchenius longissipes</i>					
		F2537	<i>Planarchaea longissipes</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
Planarchaeidae	<i>Eomysmauchenius dubius</i>					
		F2993	<i>Eomysmauchenius dubius</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
Planarchaeidae	<i>Planarchaea pilosa</i>					
		F2536	<i>Planarchaea pilosa</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
Planarchaeidae	<i>Planarchaea ovata</i>					
		F2940	<i>Planarchaea ovata</i>	F	Burmese amber	X
Planarchaeidae	<i>Planarchaea oblonga</i>					
		F2939	<i>Planarchaea oblonga</i>	F	Burmese amber	X
Planarchaeidae	<i>Planarchaea paucidentatus</i>					
		F1924	<i>Planarchaea paucidentatus</i>	F	Burmese amber	X
Planarchaeidae	<i>Planarchaea kopp</i>					
		F2522	<i>Planarchaea kopp</i>	F or juv.	Burmese amber	X
Planarchaeidae	<i>Planarchaea incompleta</i>					
		F3647	<i>Planarchaea incompleta</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
Planarchaeidae	<i>Planarchaea</i> , indet.*					
		F3062	<i>Planarchaea</i> sp.	F	Burmese amber	
Planarchaeidae	<i>Planarchaea</i> , new species					
		AMNH-JCZ-Bu-491	<i>Planarchaea</i> sp.	M	Burmese amber	
Planarchaeidae	<i>Platythelae longicorpus</i>					
		F3646	<i>Platythelae longicorpus</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
Archaeidae	<i>Burmesarchaea</i> , indet.*					
		F3414	Archaeidae, indet.	M	Burmese amber	
Archaeidae	<i>Burmesarchaea grimaldii</i>					
		F2521	<i>Burmesarchaea grimaldii</i>	F	Burmese amber	
		F2534	<i>Burmesarchaea grimaldii</i>	M	Burmese amber	
		F2519	<i>Burmesarchaea grimaldii</i>	M	Burmese amber	
		F3748	<i>Burmesarchaea</i> sp.	M	Burmese amber	
		F3746	<i>Burmesarchaea</i> sp.	F	Burmese amber	
		AMNH-Bu-256	<i>Burmesarchaea grimaldii</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
Archaeidae	<i>Burmesarchaea gibber</i>					
		F2980	<i>Burmesarchaea gibber</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
Archaeidae	<i>Burmesarchaea gibbosa</i>					
		F2989	<i>Burmesarchaea gibbosa</i>	F	Burmese amber	X
Archaeidae	<i>Burmesarchaea pseudogibber</i>					
		F2520	<i>Burmesarchaea pseudogibber</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
Archaeidae	<i>Burmesarchaea caudata</i>					
		F2709	<i>Burmesarchaea caudata</i>	F	Burmese amber	X
Archaeidae	<i>Burmesarchaea gibberoides</i>					
		F2979	<i>Burmesarchaea gibberoides</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
Archaeidae	<i>Burmesarchaea pustulata</i>					
		F2943	<i>Burmesarchaea pustulata</i>	M	Burmese amber	X
Archaeidae	<i>Burmesarchaea</i> , indet.*					
		F3409	<i>Burmesarchaea</i> , indet.	M	Burmese amber	
Archaeidae	<i>Burmesarchaea</i> , indet.*					
		F3408	<i>Burmesarchaea</i> , indet.	F	Burmese amber	
Archaeidae	<i>Burmesarchaea</i> , new species					
		USNMPAL72337	<i>Burmesarchaea</i> , indet.	F	Burmese amber	

Table S3 continued.

Archaeidae	<i>Baltarchaea conica</i>					
		F3416	<i>Baltarchaea conica</i>	M	Baltic amber	
		F2171	<i>Baltarchaea conica</i>	F	Baltic amber	
		F2172	<i>Baltarchaea</i> sp. indet.	juv.	Baltic amber	
		SMF-Be-1742	<i>Baltarchaea conica</i>	juv.	Baltic amber	
Archaeidae	Archaeidae, new species					
		F2170	<i>Archaea</i> sp.	F	Baltic amber	
Archaeidae	<i>Myrmecarchaea antecessor</i>					
		Carbuccia et al , 2020	<i>Myrmecarchaea antecessor</i>	M	Oise amber	X
Archaeidae	<i>Myrmecarchaea</i> sp.					
		BSIP-41985	<i>Myrmecarchaea</i> sp.	juv.	Cambay amber	
Archaeidae	<i>Myrmecarchaea pediculus</i>					
		GPI-4338-S3907	<i>Myrmecarchaea pediculus</i>	juv.	Baltic amber	X
Archaeidae	<i>Myrmecarchaea petiolus</i>					
		GPI-4337-S3999	<i>Myrmecarchaea petiolus</i>	juv.	Baltic amber	X
Archaeidae	<i>Eoarchaea hyperoptica</i>					
		SMF-Be-1757	<i>Eoarchaea hyperoptica</i>	F	Baltic amber	
		SMF-Be-1755	<i>Eoarchaea hyperoptica</i>	juv.	Baltic amber	
		SMF-Be-5274	<i>Eoarchaea hyperoptica</i>	juv.	Baltic amber	
		SMF-Be-1753	<i>Eoarchaea hyperoptica</i>	F	Baltic amber	
		SMF-Be-1754	<i>Eoarchaea hyperoptica</i>	F	Baltic amber	
		SMF-Be-5273	<i>Eoarchaea hyperoptica</i>	F	Baltic amber	
		SMF-Be-5272	<i>Eoarchaea hyperoptica</i>	F	Baltic amber	
		SMF-Be-5277	<i>Eoarchaea hyperoptica</i>	F or juv.	Baltic amber	
Archaeidae	<i>Eoarchaea vidua</i>					
		SMNG-07/36290	<i>Eoarchaea vidua</i>	F	Baltic amber	X
		SMF-Be-2299	<i>Archaea laevigata</i>	F	Baltic amber	
Archaeidae	<i>Archaea compacta</i>					
		SMF-Be-1736	<i>Archaea compacta</i>	F	Baltic amber	
		SMNG-07/36290	<i>Archaea compacta</i>	F	Baltic amber	
Archaeidae	<i>Archaea paradoxa</i>					
		SMF-Be-5095	<i>Archaea paradoxa</i>	F	Baltic amber	
		SMF-Be-1741	<i>Archaea paradoxa</i>	M	Baltic amber	
		SMF-Be-1739	<i>Archaea paradoxa</i>	M	Baltic amber	
		SMF-Be-1740	<i>Archaea paradoxa</i>	M	Baltic amber	
		SMF-Be-5079	<i>Archaea paradoxa</i>	M	Baltic amber	
		SMF-Be-1738	<i>Archaea paradoxa</i>	M	Baltic amber	
		SMF-Be-5084	<i>Archaea paradoxa</i>	M	Baltic amber	
		SMF-Be-1624	<i>Archaea paradoxa</i>	F	Baltic amber	
		MBA1669	<i>Archaea paradoxa</i>	F	Baltic amber	
Archaeidae	<i>Saxonarchaea dentata</i>					
		MBA602	<i>Saxonarchaea dentata</i>	M	Bitterfeld amber	
		SMNG-07/36290	<i>Saxonarchaea dentata</i>	F	Bitterfeld amber	X
Archaeidae	<i>Patarchaea muralis</i>					
		Selden, Huang & Ren, 2008	<i>Patarchaea muralis</i>	F & M	Jiulongshan Formation	X
Archaeidae	<i>Jurarchaea zherikhini</i>					
		Eskov, 1987	<i>Jurarchaea zherikhini</i>	F	Karabastau Formation	X
Palpimanoidea, indet.	<i>Sinaranea metaxyostraca</i>					
		Selden, Huang & Ren, 2008; Selden, Huang, Garwood, 2020	<i>Sinaranea metaxyostraca</i>	M	Jiulongshan Formation	X
Palpimanoidea, indet.	<i>Sinaranea brevicrus</i>					
		Selden, Huang & Ren, 2008; Selden, Huang, Garwood, 2020	<i>Sinaranea brevicrus</i>	F & M	Jiulongshan Formation	X
Palpimanoidea, indet.	<i>Seppo koponeni</i>					
		Selden & Dunlop, 2014	<i>Seppo koponeni</i>	F?	Klein Lehmhagen	X
Palpimanoidea, indet.	<i>Onychopalpus thomisoides</i>					
		Selden, Huang, Garwood, 2020	<i>Onychopalpus thomisoides</i>	juv.	Jiulongshan Formation	X
Palpimanoidea, indet.	<i>Caestaranea jurassica</i>					
		Selden, Huang, Garwood, 2020	<i>Caestaranea jurassica</i>	F & M	Jiulongshan Formation	X

Figure S1. Strict consensus phylogeny resulting from Parsimony analysis of only morphological data. Bootstrap values greater than 50% are reported at nodes. Extant taxa are shown in bold, and remaining taxa are fossils.

Figure S2. Consensus phylogeny resulting from Likelihood analysis of only morphological data. Branch support values for Shimodaira–Hasegawa-like approximate likelihood ratio test and ultrafast bootstrapping are reported at nodes. Extant taxa are shown in bold, and remaining taxa are fossils.

0.07

Figure S3. Strict consensus phylogeny resulting from Parsimony analysis of only molecular data, at 50% occupancy. Bootstrap values greater than 50% are reported at nodes.

Figure S4. Consensus phylogeny resulting from Likelihood analysis of only molecular data, at 50% occupancy. Branch support values for Shimodaira–Hasegawa-like approximate likelihood ratio test and ultrafast bootstrapping are reported at nodes.

Figure S5. Strict consensus phylogeny resulting from Parsimony analysis of only molecular data, at 70% occupancy. Bootstrap values greater than 50% are reported at nodes.

Figure S6. Consensus phylogeny resulting from Likelihood analysis of only molecular data, at 70% occupancy. Branch support values for Shimodaira–Hasegawa-like approximate likelihood ratio test and ultrafast bootstrapping are reported at nodes.

Figure S7. Strict consensus phylogeny resulting from Parsimony analysis of combined morphological and molecular data (total evidence). Molecular data is at 50% occupancy. Bootstrap values greater than 50% are reported at nodes. Extant taxa are shown in bold, and remaining taxa are fossils.

2.0

Figure S8. Strict consensus phylogeny resulting from Parsimony analysis of combined morphological and molecular data (total evidence). Molecular data is at 70% occupancy. Bootstrap values greater than 50% are reported at nodes. Extant taxa are shown in bold, and remaining taxa are fossils.

Figure S9. Consensus phylogeny resulting from Likelihood analysis of combined morphological and molecular data (total evidence). Molecular data is at 50% occupancy. Branch support values for Shimodaira–Hasegawa-like approximate likelihood ratio test and ultrafast bootstrapping are reported at nodes. Extant taxa are shown in bold, and remaining taxa are fossils.

Figure S10. Consensus phylogeny resulting from Likelihood analysis of combined morphological and molecular data (total evidence). Molecular data is at 70% occupancy. Branch support values for Shimodaira–Hasegawa-like approximate likelihood ratio test and ultrafast bootstrapping are reported at nodes. Extant taxa are shown in bold, and remaining taxa are fossils.

Figure S11. Ancestral area estimations from the DEC model biogeography analysis of eight areas. Colored squares at terminals represent the distribution of terminal taxa, at nodes represent the most likely ancestral range, and at corners represent the most likely range of the two descendant lineages. Extant taxa are shown in bold, and remaining taxa are fossils. Scale = millions of years before present.

Figure S12. Ancestral area estimations from the DEC model biogeography analysis of eight areas. Pie charts represent the percentage of the most likely ancestral geographic ranges at each node. Colored squares at terminals represent the distribution of terminal taxa. Extant taxa are shown in bold, and remaining taxa are fossils. Scale = millions of years before present.

Figure S13. Ancestral area estimations from the DEC model biogeography analysis of three areas. Colored squares at terminals represent the distribution of terminal taxa, at nodes represent the most likely ancestral range, and at corners represent the most likely range of the two descendant lineages. Extant taxa are shown in bold, and remaining taxa are fossils. Scale = millions of years before present.

Figure S14. Ancestral area estimations from the DEC model biogeography analysis of three areas. Pie charts represent the percentage of the most likely ancestral geographic ranges at each node. Colored squares at terminals represent the distribution of terminal taxa. Extant taxa are shown in bold, and remaining taxa are fossils. Scale = millions of years before present.

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